

Electrochemistry of dihydroxyflavones – a DPP study

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The electrochemical behaviour of four different dihydroxyflavones were studied by differential pulse polarographic (DPP) method in acidic and alkaline media with tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) as supporting electrolyte and Britton-Robinson buffer and the kinetic parameters were evaluated.

The biological electron transfer reactions and the electrochemical electron transfer reactions have many things in common. Both involve essentially heterogeneous electron transfer, pH and temperature dependent and occur at electrode/electrolyte interface or at membrane/solution interface. Hence explanations based on electrochemistry have played an important role in interpreting and understanding the biological phenomena.

The present communication which is in continuation of the work^{1,2} on electrochemistry of flavonoid compounds, describes the differential pulse polarographic study of 3,7-, 3,6-, 6,2'- and 5,2'- dihydroxyflavones in DMF/ B.R. buffer in TBAB supporting electrolyte.

Results and discussion

The dihydroxyflavones gave a single, well-defined cathodic wave as expected³. The limiting current varied linearly with concentration of the flavones and also with the square root of the mercury column height, indicating that the waves are diffusion controlled. The electrochemical reduction process was found to be irreversible as evidenced from the variation of the depolarizer, log plot analysis and disobedience of Tome's criteria⁴.

The half wave potential becomes slightly more negative with increase in pH (Table 1). The kinetic parameters such as diffusion co-efficient (D) and heterogeneous forward rate constant (K_{f}^0) were calculated using Meites and Israel equation⁵. The values of αn_a , diffusion co-efficient and heterogeneous forward rate constant decreased with increase in pH. This may be attributed to the decrease in availability of protons with increase in pH. Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out and the course of the two-electron keto reduction process was monitored by UV-visible absorption peak at 530 nm.

The electrode process is considered to be a mono anion

radical formation by the addition of one electron followed by protonation of the ion-radical. The uptake of the second electron occurs with no further requirement of activation energy so that only a single two-electron wave is observed and further, protonation leads to the product⁶.

Experimental

UV-visible Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model EZ 301 and polarographic analyzer CL362 Elico Ltd., Hyderabad, India were used. The glass capillary characteristics, $m = 28.88 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t = 1 \text{ s}$ under open circuit was used in polarographic measurements. A saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode and because of poor aqueous solubility, 60% DMF was used as solvent. Test solutions were prepared in solutions of different pH, thermostated ($298 \pm 1 \text{ K}$) and deaerated before measurement. Owing to the instability of flavonoid solutions in alkaline pH, solid compound was added to cell solution just before measurement.

The controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in a 250 ml beaker and a ceramic diaphragm ($14.5 \text{ cm} \times 4.5 \text{ cm}$) was used to separate the anolyte from the catholyte. Dihydroxyflavones were purchased from Research organics, Chennai and recrystallised from methanol. The Britton-Robinson buffer was prepared from 0.04 M acetic acid, phosphoric acid and boric acid and the pH was adjusted with 0.2 N NaOH.

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Note

Table 1. Kinetic parameters of dihydroxyflavones

Flavone	Medium	pH	$E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA	αn_a	D $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$K_{f,h}^0$
3,7-Dihydroxyflavone	60% DMF/ B.R. buffer	2.5	-1.462	0.5835	0.2362	3.5946×10^{-6}	1.217×10^{-8}
	60% DMF/ B.R. buffer	8.65	-1.486	0.2931	0.2312	2.1361×10^{-8}	1.470×10^{-9}
3,6-Dihydroxyflavone	60% DMF/ B.R. buffer	2.5	-1.480	2.1816	0.2417	3.5946×10^{-6}	1.2170×10^{-8}
	60% DMF/ B.R. buffer	8.65	-1.594	2.5773	0.2371	3.9967×10^{-6}	4.9362×10^{-9}
6,2'-Dihydroxyflavone	60% DMF/ B.R. buffer	2.5	-1.674	2.1107	0.2294	9755×10^{-3}	6.4241×10^{-7}
	60% DMF/ B.R. buffer	8.65	-1.686	2.0276	0.2021	5.319×10^{-4}	3.6621×10^{-8}
5,2'-Dihydroxyflavone	60% DMF/ B.R. buffer	2.5	-1.838	2.8583	0.2343	4.267×10^{-3}	6.8830×10^{-7}
	60%DMF/ B.R. buffer	8.65	-1.850	2.1258	0.2305	1.1726×10^{-4}	4.324×10^{-8}

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